

About The Holy Steps of Samarkand

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Annotation: This article describes the educational significance of the objects of pilgrimage tourism in Samarkand region, in particular, the shrine of Imam Ali Sogdi. The article also contains information about Imam Ali Sogdi, who was recognized as the great Imam of his time.

Keywords: Pilgrimage tourism, Samarkand region, Islamic theology, scholar, Imam Ali Sogdi, spiritual heritage, shrine.

Introduction

The city of Samarkand, which is a contemporary of Ancient Rome, has always attracted foreign tourists with its objects of material and spiritual heritage. In Samarkand itself there are more than 490 objects of tangible cultural heritage, of which 14 are ancient archaeological settlements, 417 architectural structures, 36 monuments of monumental art, 23 attractions. The number of such objects in the Samarkand region is 1626, of which 975 are archaeological, 581 are architectural, 36 are monuments of monumental art and 34 are sights. These objects indicate the great potential for the development of the tourism industry in Samarkand.

Materials and Methods

The city of Samarkand has been famous for its shrines since ancient times. In the city there is the Shahi Zinda complex, which contains the tomb of Abu Jafar Kusam ibn Abbas Ibn Abdulmuttalib Ibn Hisham al-Qurayshi, to whom the tomb of the prophet is attributed, the mausoleum of the Sultan of Hadith studies Imam Bukhari, the mentor of Imam Bukhari - Imam Dorimi, Imam Moturudi, who created a separate school in the region science of words, Imam Burhaniddin Marghinoni, the greatest scholar of fiqh, Imam Abul Qasim al-Hakim al-Samarkandi, Imam Fakih Abu Lays Samarkandi, Sheikh Burhaniddin Sagarji, Khoja Ahrori Vali, Makhdumi Azam, as well as several scientists, as well as teacher of the Sufi tariqa, There are especially many tombs of saints; the presence of the Chokardiza cemetery, where scholars and theologians are buried, indicates that Samarkand is one of the holy cities not only of the earthly, but also of the Islamic world. Najmuddin Umar al-Nasafi's book "Kandiya" talks about the influence of only one Chokardiza cemetery: "there is no big cemetery except the Baqiya cemetery in Medina and the Muallo cemetery in Makka, except the chokardiza cemetery in Samarkand...". In the Chokardiza cemetery,

where the largest number of great scientists of the Islamic world are buried, there are the graves of many mujtahid scholars, muhaddiths and holy sahibkaromats, as Abu Tohirhoja says in his work "Samaria": "the kings smeared the earth of ul-mina, like antimony, on their eyes"[1;36].

Results

Another shrine of Samarkand is the tomb of Imam Ali Sogdiy in the village of Kumushkent, Okdarya district. The attitude towards the tomb of Imam Ali Sogdiy changed after we gained independence. In the history of this step, the ardent scientist from Samarkand K. Kataev conducts research. The research of this scientist clarified the information about the sanctuary of Imam Ali Sogdiy.

There were also many inaccuracies in the sources referring to Imam Ali Sogdi, in particular in "Samaria" by Abu Tohirhoaji, "Kitabul-ansob" by Abu Saad Abdulkarim al-Samani. In addition, "Tazkira of the saints and scribes of Turon" by S. Mustafoyev and M. Ablav also contains inaccuracies in references to Imam Ali Sogdiy. They said: "Imam Ali Sogdiy is also famous for his noble career. Imam Al-Marghinani is considered one of the disciples of his highness"[2;525]. Accurate scientific information about Imam Ali Sogdiy is described in Kataev's research.

In the ancient cemetery in the village of Kumushkent there is a Sufi mausoleum of Imam Ali Sogdiy, in which, in addition to the imam, there are the graves of Sheikh Yaminbob, Sheikh Alishaih and Sheikh Mavdud, teacher of the Yassawi tariqa of Sufism, as evidenced by many sources, in particular, the work of Abu Tahirhoja "Samaria" "

Kattaev describes the place of Allah in Islamic theology as follows: "Mawlana Burhaniddin is a disciple of the marginal Hazrat Najmiddin Umar an Nasafi; and this man is a student of Fakhrul Islam Ali Pazdawi; and this man is a disciple of Shamsul aimma halwai; and this man is a student of Imam Ali Sogdiy"[3;62]. These great scholars of jurisprudence lived mainly in the 11th and 12th centuries. So, Imam Ali Sogdiy was the teacher of such great lawyer.

The work of Abu Saad Abdulkarim al-Samani "Kitabul-ansab" provides information about Imam Ali Sogdiy: "this man, an imam, a scientist, had no equal in science"[3;63].

According to Abu Tahirhoja's "Samaria", Imam Ali Sogdiy was the son of Hasan bin Sheikh Muhammad Sogdiy. At one time, the village of Kumushkent was called Sogdiy. Therefore, the Sogdian proportion is given. It is stated that he was educated in Baghdad. There are many mentors, usually two are Imam al-Karhi and Imam Khalil al-Bukhari who are better known. Works such as his "commentary on Siyari Kabir" and "Favoid" were popular among legal scholars.

In the Middle Ages, this shrine was considered very prestigious. Kattaev says: "in the "Zafar-nama" of Sharafiddin Ali Yazdi it is said that ten thousand soldiers and ambassadors sent by Genghis Khan Emir Hussein from the rulers of Transoxiana, with the aim of concluding a truce with the Amir Timur, will land at tombs of Hazrat Ali. This story is described in another source about Amir Temur, in the work of Nizamiddin Shami, exactly as described in the above source. Thus, judging by the admission of these two reliable sources on the history of Amir Temur, the fact that the rulers

of Transoxiana did not dare to do something as great as a truce by coming to the tomb, like Ali, shows how great the position of this tomb is”[3;58].

Conclusion

To summarize, we can say that, first of all, the city and region of Samarkand have rich historical, cultural and spiritual sites, which serve as a sufficient foundation for the widespread development of tourism in our country. Secondly, Samarkand, with its numerous pilgrimage sites, has great potential for the development of domestic tourism. Thirdly, it is necessary to develop fundamental research to study the scientific heritage of Imam Ali Sogdiy, recognized in the Islamic world as a great imam. Fourthly, the shrine of Imam Ali Sogdiy is also an important tourist pilgrimage site in the province, and serious attention must be paid to its renovation and research into the scientific heritage of the great people buried there. In addition to economic benefits, domestic pilgrimage tourism serves to increase the perception and understanding of our national values, cultural heritage in the thinking of our citizens, especially young people, and to create a sense of national pride and pride.

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